

Title	Europa World of Learning 2020
Sub Title	The International Guide To The Academic World.
Editor	Europa Publications
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Language	English

INTRODUCTION

The Europa World of Learning is a well-established and respected reference work listing higher education, research and other academic institutions throughout the world, published annually in print and updated quarterly online.

The first edition published in 1947, it has since become established as an authoritative reference work on academic institutions all over the world. This is comprehensive and easy to use, this is an essential source of information on higher education on a world-wide scale. The World of Learning is the classic reference book. This will

remain the one absolutely standard directory for every higher education and related institution throughout the world, as well as for anybody who deals with these institutions to any region

SCOPE

The Europa World of learning is one of the world's learning reference works. Updated to the *highest* editorials standards, entries are sourced directly from the organization to ensure accurate and reliable information. The accreditation status of every university and college is verified before its entry is approved.

Every type of academic institution is covered, including over:

- 14,000 universities and colleges
- 6,500 research institutes
- 4,900 museums and art galleries
- 5,000 learned societies
- 4,000 libraries and archives
- 850 regulatory and representative bodies
- Details more than 200,000 staff and officials
- Information on about 600 international cultural, scientific and educational organizations
- Covers every important library giving the number of volumes held and outstanding features of the collection

"... this offers quite unrivalled coverage, both for its comprehensiveness and accuracy. It is truly a bible for higher education throughout the world." - *Reference Reviews*

TREATMENT

- Each Entries provides information about higher education system learned society, and international organizations
- All entries provide: Name; address; telephone numbers-mail and Internet addresses; principal personnel; activities and publications, where available.
- Professors at major universities are listed by name, together with the subjects in which they specialize.
- Exceptional as a worldwide academic mailing list.
- Completely revised and updated throughout the year.
- Abbreviations are also given

ARRANGEMENTS

- Name of countries are arranged according to alphabetically.

- Type of institutes in classified order starting with “General institute”
- In some type of institute segregation (division) is done state wise also alphabetically
- Name of institute or universities written alphabetically
- Index of institute given at end is also arranged alphabetically

FORMAT

- It is available in print as well as online

PRINT FORMAT

- It has hardcover binding
- It is in two volumes

Volume 1

Part 1: Introductory Essays

Part 2: International Organizations

Part 3: Afghanistan- Nigeria.

Volume 2

Part 4: Norway- Zimbabwe

- There are three columns per page
- Heading is in bold face and sub Heading in light face
- Print is clear and legible

ONLINE FEATURES

The online version is fully searchable, and features over 33,000 entries which contain over 40,000 institutional web links. Additionally the database also features topical essays on the world of higher education.

- There is also an archive of introductory essays which subscribers may download, taken from the current print edition as well as previous print editions of The Europa World of Learning.

- The Online version of The Europa World of Learning builds on this success by providing a *full range* of sophisticated search and browse functions, and regular updates of content.

DRAWBACKS

- It is not available in CD ROM

CONCLUSION

The world of learning is unrivaled in its depth of practical and reliable information. For users, seeking easy to use, one stop source for information on academic institution located around the world, the world of learning is quite useful, well index well edited and is the best single reference book on international scholarship.

"Simply the best reference guide to the academic world." - *Book News Inc.*

REFERENCES

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